

Reconstructing ‘Self and Identity’ in the Selected Novels of Janhavi Barua

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Abstract: In the last decade we have witnessed so many excellent writings from the North East India. This is an interesting development and what amazes more is the attention it has drawn towards the region’s writing and its people from around the world. The North East is constantly evolving; always in formation. In order to redistribute and reorganise knowledge, the discursive construction of social identities along the lines of gender, race and class has to be understood in terms of place. Also, more significant narratives are coming from the other section of the society- i.e. the women writers. These women writers provide a fertile arena for the representation of women who are stereotyped in both the affirmative and the negative. These writers have claimed equality in terms of historical specificity and to create an idiom of resistance. There have been attempts to find one’s own space within the realm of feminist imagination and culture building. The tradition of women’s writing in English in North east is new with most of the writings by women taking off only after the advent of the British rule in the region and with the introduction of formal education. Among the Northeast states there is a shared commonality even though the region is highly heterogeneous. The rise of the English fiction from the region and short stories has proliferated and the contributions of women writers are immense. Temsula Ao , Easterine Kire, Mamang Dai, Mitra Phukan and Janhavi Barua are some of the prominent writers from the region. In the present paper we shall focus on the works of Janhavi Barua who have always been close to themes of homecoming and finding one’s own identity. Also another focus of Barua is that of family and the complexities of this unique entity which is clearly reflected in her works.

Keywords: Identity, self, displacement, patriarchy, womanhood, resilience

Janhavi Barua is a Bengaluru based Assamese writer whose latest book *Undertow* (2020) was recently long listed for the JCB Prize 2020. Other notable works include *Next Door* (2010), *Rebirth* (2010). Barua’s works have always been close to themes of home and homecoming and of identity and finding one’s own roots. Also, another arena of interest of Barua is that of family and the complexities of this unique entity which is clearly reflected in her works. The paper is primary based on migration, quest for identity, kinship and redefining women hood. Barua’s novels are mainly set in Assam and mainly focus on the themes of home, family, belongingness and finding one self. In her novel *Undertow* (2020) the main protagonist Loya is a solitary, sincere twenty five years old research student with restless stirrings in heart. She leaves her home in Bangalore and sets off to Assam. Her Doctor mother Rukmini who originally hails from Assam, relocates herself in Bangalore after her marriage to Alex. She was cast away from home for marrying against Usha’s (her mother) wishes. Torun, the father arranged a simple court marriage and unable to displease his wife Usha, he too cut ties with Rukmini. Loya, Rukmini’s daughter after twenty five years later lands in Yellow House in search for answers from Torun, her maternal grandfather and from the place which was home to Rukmini. She ends up not only knowing herself better but also learns about human bonds, family ties and complexities of human relationships. It is Loya’s quest for her identity of which you are as a person, what you stand for and where it is that you feel accepted.

In yet another novel of Janhavi Barua’s “*Rebirth*” (2010) is the portrayal of Kaberi, who fights an internal battle of coming out of her passive existence and embraces her new found identity. Kaberi all through her life suppressed her individuality and let others make decisions for her. Writers like Mamang

Dai and Temsula Ao on the other hand, have portrayed their female protagonist as very strong women who take the course of life in their own hands. Barua's Kaberi is set apart from these women probably intentionally by the author, so as to show ripe for the much needed "rebirth" and finding her identity thereby breaking the shackles of all her past inhibitors. The "rebirth" of Barua's protagonist owes a lot to her contact with the other women- her friends, mother, aunt, maid who gives her words of wisdom and courage to carry forward in life. The unborn child is the only one whom she is comfortable to confide in. We learn of Protagonist fears, hopes and dreams that she confides to her unborn child. Her final decision to take the course of her life in her own hands is the ultimate transformation to establish her own identity. She is no longer ready to forgive, forget and adjust to Ron's way of life. Her "Rebirth" is connected to "the birth of her child". Her identity towards establishing her own identity is not sudden but progresses gradually to a climax. In her search for her true 'self' Barua's protagonist realizes her own potentials and emerges as a strong and determined woman.

Contemporary studies on migration in recent times have shifted from categorizing texts with themes of migration with the status of exile to analysing texts as literature of migration (Mardorossian15). The story is a first person narrative and reflects the thoughts, fears, hopes and dilemma of Kaberi to her unborn child. Here the focus is on the reconstruction of self (Kaberi). The protagonist migrates from the North east state of Assam to the silicon city of Bangalore in the southern state of India. Kaberi is altogether introduced to a new location, culture and language. And of all she migrates from a rural middle class household to a wealthy class. As the story moves forward she is deserted by her husband for another woman. She starts reflecting on her past through her memory and offers us glimpse of her past life based on this recollection. The glimpses of the past and present are clearly juxtaposed and the readers are presented with both the past and present life simultaneously. The juxtaposition is a reflection of both the culture of Assam that she has left far behind in the past and the corporate society of Bangalore that Kaberi has embraced post her marriage. On the other hand, the infidelity and desertion acts as a catalyst for her to rekindle her identity and she considers going back to her hometown. *Rebirth (2010)* is a novel of temporal dislocation in the narrative where the past and present are interconnected in which anxiety of the Protagonist rests in the anticipation of the future rather than the loss of the past. In yet another novel "*Undertow*" (2010) there is multiple facets of the underlying theme of migration. Rukmini migrates to Bangalore after her marriage to Alex who is a Christian Malayali. And this was the reason she was cast out of home. Caste, religion and colour were important to Usha than her daughter's happiness. Rukmini in Bangalore post her marriage had always been a half insider. She was disliked by Ammachi who always was of the view that had Alex married a girl of one's own community, things would have been better. Loya, half Assamese and half Malayali always repressed her thoughts and emotions especially after her Parent's divorce. In the beginning she is empty as she tries to ascertain her roots and the desire to get the answers lands her to "The Yellow House" home to her mother Rukmini. A girl alienated from her roots, she sets on a journey of self-exploration and develops strong bonds with her maternal grandfather Torun Goswami and rest of the people in between an indigenous person who has sunk his roots on one place and a migrant who has no tangible roots.

Writings from the North east and its representation of women are truly liberating and celebratory for the readers. The writings highlight the issues of oppression, subjugation, patriarchy, silences, identity crisis, searching for roots etc. Barua's depiction of strong women characters in her novel redefines the concept of Womanhood. Hence, the discursive construction of social identities along the lines of gender, race and class has to be understood in terms of the place. In "*Rebirth*" the chief protagonist Kaberi emerges as a strong woman at the end who defies the social norms of Patriarchy. The other empowered character in Barua's novel is that of Joya and she is everything that Kaberi is not. She demonstrates strong will and free opinion. She voiced out her opinions and took part in revolutionary marches, organizing blackouts and taking the lead in "andolans". On the other hand, in "*Undertow*" Rukmini had been patient and obedient daughter to Torun and Usha Goswami. But after she falls in love with Alex, a Christian

Malayali from Bangalore and defies the region, religion, caste and systems of hierarchy. She takes the course of life in her own hands and marries against her Parent's wishes. She continues her life with her daughter Loya in Bangalore even after her husband deserts her. The character of Loya also surprises us often when she defies the social constructs and surprises her Grandfather often during her short stay in the Yellow House. In fact, Loya questions Torun for her inactions, for letting Usha cast out her dearest Rukmini.

Lastly, Barua is very much aware of the concerns that come along with being a woman in her novels she very sensibly deals with the feminine characters. This woman characters has garnered greater visibility as they shun the patriarchal norms and redefines the concept of womanhood. Her characters are on a quest for self-discovery and self-realization. The present paper also creates a platform of critical analysis regarding the new trends of Women's writings from the North East. It discusses how the Protagonist relocates itself and discusses on the value of compassion, nurturance and peace-making. Barua redefines womanhood in response to the exploitation, domination and devaluation of women by the Patriarchal society. It primarily discusses Janhavi Barua as an excellent writer and has analysed the complexities of her characters in her novels in terms of self-discovery, self-recovery and resilience. Barua portrays a poignant portrait of family and all that it contains. Her writings do not have to be loud to be heard and she achieves great intensity with the greatest of delicacy and restraint.

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